

1 **Therapeutic targeting in colorectal cancer for the treatment of liver metastasis: TIGIT.**

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6 The liver is the most common site of metastasis in patients with colorectal cancer (1-5). We recently
7 utilized whole transcriptome technologies to define the full complement of differentially expressed kinases
8 and phosphatases in HER2+ breast cancer: in the primary tumor, and in metastasis to the CNS (6-8).
9 Measuring total transcription with RNA-sequencing and microarray in metastasis and the cancer (primary
10 tumor) from which they are derived enables rational design and development of novel chemotherapies
11 with optimized therapeutic index (9). Here we utilize whole transcriptome technologies (10, 11) to
12 measure total transcription in the liver metastases of humans with colorectal cancer. We describe a
13 therapeutic target that is up-regulated and differentially expressed in liver metastasis in humans with
14 colorectal cancer, *TIGIT*, as a candidate therapeutic target for the medical management of liver metastasis
15 in human colorectal cancer.
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We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the transcriptome (RNA), and epigenetic modification (eg., CpG-DNA) of humans with cancer. This includes the primary tumor, the source of the transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - subtypes of the primary tumor, including luminal, basal and HER2+ forms in breast cancer, and adeno and squamous forms of NSCLC in lung cancer, "regional" metastasis to the liver, metastasis to distant sites, including the lungs, the liver and the brain, and the circulating tumor stem cell. Here we measure total transcription in metastasis to the liver to discover and describe a therapeutic target identified through rigorous study of the liver metastatic transcriptome in colorectal cancer: a therapeutic target that is up-regulated and metastasis-specific, providing ideal therapeutic index to minimize toxicity and maximize efficacy: TIGIT.

Results

Figure 1: TIGIT is differentially expressed in liver metastasis in humans with colorectal cancer.

I. Liver metastasis and primary tumors from humans with colorectal cancer.

n=4 primary tumors from humans with colorectal cancer

n=3 liver metastases from humans with colorectal cancer

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
201633	8.23E-02	0.646	-1.7376584	-1.12314	280.54	TIGIT	4470/19486	77.1

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the primary tumors of the colorectum and in liver metastases of humans with colorectal cancer, we discovered differential expression of T cell immunoreceptor with Ig and ITIM domains, encoded by *TIGIT* in metastasis to the liver in humans with colorectal cancer (**Chart 1**). The expression of TIGIT changed more than 75% of the human colorectal cancer (CRC) liver metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 19,486 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of TIGIT messenger RNA in CRC liver metastases, demonstrating up-regulation of TIGIT during disease progression in colorectal cancer.

II. Liver metastasis in patients with colorectal cancer.

n=10 primary tumors from humans with colorectal cancer

n=10 liver metastases from humans with colorectal cancer

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
201633	2.17E-02	0.262	-2.2962685	-0.60114621	160.19	TIGIT	1890/15341	87.7

Through measurement of total transcription in the liver metastases of humans with colorectal cancer as compared to primary tumors of the colon and rectum, we validated differential expression of TIGIT in human colorectal cancer (**Chart 2**). The expression of TIGIT here changed more than 85% of the liver metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 15,341 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of TIGIT messenger RNA in liver metastases, demonstrating up-regulation of TIGIT during disease progression and metastasis in humans with colorectal cancer.

1 Thus, differential and increased expression of TIGIT defines the liver metastatic transcriptome in
2 human colorectal cancer.

3 **Discussion**

4 Adjunctive treatments in medical oncology limit the emergence of resistant tumor clones during
5 treatment with a second agent (whether neoadjuvantive chemotherapy or a targeted therapy like
6 trastuzumab). Inhibitors of TIGIT, once evaluated for toxicity and safety, can immediately be tested for
7 efficacy in patients with liver metastasis who have failed previous treatment, with the goal of identifying the
8 most effective inhibitors of liver metastasis in humans with colorectal cancer. A multi-kinase approach
9 delivered in conjunction with chemotherapies that target dNTP synthesis, replication of the daughter
10 strand and activity at the spindle at anaphase, and target *CDKN* inactivation and ATP-binding cassette
11 pump expression in resistant cases, is most likely to be most effective in limiting tumor clone resistance
12 (12).
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Methods

We utilized GSE213402 and GSE179979 for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in metastasis to the liver and in primary tumors from humans with colorectal cancer using RNA-sequencing data (public and published) and R-based computational methods.